
A Review Of Avifaunal Diversity In Indian Wetlands And Its Impact On Conservation Using GIS

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Abstract:

Wetlands of India are vital and unique habitat of aquatic faunal biodiversity especially avifaunal diversity like waterfowl, estimated to be 58.2 million hectares in area. Providing the food, migratory routs and habitat for these water birds is one of the most important functions performed by the wetlands. These wetlands are now under threat due to encroachment, silting, weed infestation and pollution. The review deals with the information of avifaunal diversity inhabiting in Indian wetlands and causes and consequences of wetland losses. It also provides a use of remote sensing and Geographic Information System (GIS) tools in mapping for the conservation of wetlands.

Keywords: Wetland, Avifauna, Diversity, GIS, Conservation.

Introduction:

A wetland is a land areas saturated with water, either permanently or seasonally, and form a distinct ecosystem for large faunal diversity. The water found in wetlands can be salty, freshwater, or brackish. Wetland eco-system constitutes an integral part of cultural and biodiversity landscape of India. Wetlands in India occupy 58.2 million hectares, including areas under wet paddy cultivation (Directory of Indian Wetlands). Of the estimated 58.2 million hectares of wetlands in India, 40.9 million hectares are under rice cultivation (Anon. 1993). Eighty percent of India's 4240 Sq km of mangrove forests occur in the Sunderbans and the Andaman and Nicobar Islands (Anon. 1991). Most of the wetlands are natural ecosystems stabilized over the years, and have retained their natural characteristics (Choudhury, 2000). The major wetland types in India include flood plains of major rivers, estuaries, freshwater

lakes, backwaters, mangroves, tanks, marshes, swamps, jheels, beels, terai, and man-made water bodies like reservoirs. Wetlands are important for environment and play vital role in Reservoirs of biodiversity, Flood control, shoreline stability, water purification and flood control. Wetlands are often described as “kidneys of the landscape” (Mitsch & Gosselink 1986). These wetlands are now under threat due to encroachment, silting, weed infestation and pollution. All these factors resulted in rise to problems like decrease in bio diversity, deterioration of water quality, sedimentation and shrinkage in areas of the wetlands led to decrease in migratory bird populations and other fauna. It is estimated that freshwater wetlands alone support 20 per cent of the known range of biodiversity in India (Deepa & Ramachandra 1999). In India 1230 bird species are found of which, around 23% are totally wetland dependent birds. Providing the food, migratory routs and habitat for

these water birds is one of the most important functions performed by wetlands. These makes critically important to save and conservation of major wetlands scientifically which is possible by using the available information. Unfortunately, many important wetlands are threatened, and water birds are under pressure from increasing human population and anthropogenic activities.

Definition of Wetlands According to Ramsar Convention:

The Convention on Wetlands of International Importance, especially as Waterfowl Habitat, or Ramsar Convention, is an international treaty designed to address global concerns regarding wetland loss and degradation.

Ramsar Convention has defined wetlands as "Areas of marsh, fen, peat land or water, whether natural or artificial, permanent or temporary with water that is static or flowing, fresh, brackish or salt, including areas of marine water the depth of which at low tide does not exceed six meters".

Table 1: Showing extent of spread of Indian wetlands (Parikh and Parikh 1999).

Wetlands in India	Area in million hectares
Area under paddy cultivation	40.9
Area suitable for fish culture	2.9
Area under capture fisheries	2.9
Mangroves	0.4
Estuaries	3.9
Backwaters	3.5
Impoundments	3.0
Total Area	58.2

Table2: Showing state wise distribution of wetlands under National Wetland Conservation & Management Programme.

State	Number of wetlands	Area (ha)
Andhra Pradesh	1	90100
Assam	2	4504
Bihar	3	11490
Chandigarh	1	148
Gujarat	8	1270875
Himachal Pradesh	5	15736
Haryana	2	288
Jammu and Kashmir	7	117325
Jharkhand	2	98965
Karnataka	7	4250
Kerala	5	213229
Madhya Pradesh	12	359814
Maharashtra	3	40298
Manipur	1	26600
Mizoram	2	285
Orissa	4	122580
Punjab	3	5648
Rajasthan	1	24000
Sikkim	6	164
Tamil Nadu	3	46283
Tripura	1	240
Uttar Pradesh	9	12083
Uttaranchal	1	800
West Bengal	5	553090

Twenty three percent of total bird species are totally wetland dependent few bird species are listed below. Avifauna species found in India have been listed by Gopal (1995).

Table 3: Showing bird species and their abundance in the major freshwater wetlands in different states of India.

Sr. No.	State	No. of Species	Threatened Species	Near Threatened Species
1	Tamil Nadu	125	3	5
2	Andhra Pradesh	139	6	8
3	MP and CG	99	5	6
4	Maharashtra	104	2	6
5	Gujarat	159	6	7
6	Rajasthan	123	6	7
7	Haryana	132	6	8
8	Punjab	90	4	2
9	Jammu and Kashmir	106	2	2
10	Himachal Pradesh	45	2	1
11	Uttar Pradesh	149	13	9
12	Bihar	95	3	3
13	West Bengal	130	6	6
14	Sikkim	30	1	0
15	Meghalaya	47	0	2
16	Assam	131	10	8
17	Manipur	46	3	2

Table 4: Showing Threatened bird species observed in major wetlands of India*.

Sr. No.	Common name	Scientific name
1.	Baers Pochard	<i>Aythya baeri</i>
2.	Baikal Teal	<i>Anas Formosa</i>
3.	Blacknecked Crane	<i>Grus nigricollis</i>
4.	Bristled Grass Warbler	<i>Chaetornis striatus</i>
5.	Dalmatian Pelican	<i>Pelecanus crispus</i>
6.	Finn,s Weaver	<i>Ploceus megarhynchus</i>
7.	Great Adjutant	<i>Leptoptilus dubius</i>
8.	Greater Spotted Eagle	<i>Aquila clanga</i>
9.	Imperial Eagle	<i>Aquila heliacea</i>
10.	Indian Skimmer	<i>Rhynchops albicollis</i>
11.	Longbilled Vulture	<i>Gyps indicus</i>
12.	Lesser Adjutant	<i>Leptoptilus javanicus</i>
13.	Lesser Kestrel	<i>Falco naummani</i>
14.	Marbled Teal	<i>Marmaronetta angustirostris</i>
15.	Masked Finfoot	<i>Helipais personata</i>
16.	Sarus Crane	<i>Gurs antigone</i>
17.	Spoonbilled Sandpiper	<i>Eurynorynchus pygmeus</i>
18.	Spotbilled Pelican	<i>Pelicanus philipensis</i>
19.	Swamp Francolin	<i>Frankolinus gularis</i>
20.	Whitebellied Heron	<i>Ardea insignis</i>
21.	Whitebellied Vulture	<i>Gyps bengalensis</i>
22.	Whitewinged Wad Duck	<i>Cairina scutulata</i>
23.	Wood Snipe	<i>Gallinaga nemoricola</i>

*Source-BNHS and WETLAND INTERNATIONAL

Threats to Wetlands:

The rapidly expanding human population, large scale changes in land use and land cover, multiple development projects and improper use of watersheds have all caused a substantial decline of wetland resources of the Indian subcontinent. Absence of reliable and updated information about extent of wetlands, their conservation values and socioeconomic importance has greatly hampered their development (Gopal, 1995).

Mapping Indian Wetlands:

For long-term conservation of wetlands, exact information. Wetland ecosystem constitutes an integral part of cultural and biodiversity landscape of India. It is estimated that 3.5 million hectares exists in the country according to the 1992-1993 study by the Space Application Centre. However, this information pertains to wetlands above 56ha in size. Past research on wetland conservation in the country has shown conclusively that micro wetlands or satellite wetlands around a bigger wetland act as a constellation of habitat mosaic for resident and migratory waterfowl. This is of special importance for inland wetland habitats in the flyways of migratory birds in the Indo-Gangetic plains and in Deccan peninsula. Often, the size of these micro wetlands is much smaller than 50ha therefore; there is a great need to map wetlands of size smaller than 50ha. Spatial information on wetlands resources is a critical and urgent need for an effective conservation of these important eco-systems harboring a diverse range fauna specially avifauna.

Use Of GIS And Remote Sensing In Wetland Conservation:

Wetlands are important habitat for avifaunal diversity, but due to various anthropogenic activities this unique habitat is under great pressure and their destruction
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results in the extinction of avifaunal diversity. There is urgent need to use both basic conservation strategy and all technological aspects for wetland conservation. Geographic Information System (GIS) is effective tool for wetland conservation and management. The applications include water resource assessment, hydrologic modeling, flood management, reservoir capacity surveys, assessment and monitoring of the environmental impacts of water resources project and water quality mapping and monitoring (Jonna 1999). Results obtained could be used in planning, inventorying and monitoring wetlands in the country (SAC, 1998). Using IRS LISS II data (Sasmal & Raju 1996) monitored the suspended load in estuarine waters of Hoogly, West Bengal in a GIS environment. Landsat TM and IRS – 1A data were used to estimate sediment load in Upper Lake, Bhopal (Raju *et al.* 1993). This study showed high relationship between the satellite as well as ground truth radiometric data and total suspended solids. GIS and remote sensing were used for the development of water resources in Sai-Gad subwatershed of Almora District, Uttar Pradesh (Mohan *et al.* 2000). Air-borne and space-borne data were used for the qualitative evaluation of ground water resources in Keonjhar district, Orissa (Das *et al.* 1997). Remote sensing, geophysical, DBTM (Digital Basement Terrain Model) and GIS (Geographic Information System) were used for sustainable utilization of water resources of Alaunja watershed, located in ‘Chotanagpur’ plateau of Bihar (Kumar 1999). The interconnectivity of wetlands and changes in it over a period of time were documented for large areas of Bangalore urban and rural districts by Deepa & Ramachandra (1999).

Conclusion:

As these wetlands are vital for sustaining the life of avifaunal diversity,

there is a great need to focus for their conservations by keeping in mind all basic and advanced technology like GIS and remote sensing.

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